

GREEN HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT ENHANCES ENVIRONMENTAL PERFORMANCE: THE ROLES OF PERSONAL MORAL NORMS AND GREEN VALUES

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Abstract

A growing concern of organizations is sustainability in the environment, especially in developing economies that are facing ecological degradation at a rate that exceeds efforts to reverse it. This study explores the influence of Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) on Environmental Performance (EP) in Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Lahore city, Pakistan. The study further examines PMN as an intervening variable in the GHRM-EP linkage, while GV is tested as a boundary condition of that relationship based on Social Cognitive Theory (Bandura, 1986). The data were obtained using purposive sampling and analyzed by Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) software SmartPLS with 281 respondents. Results showed that GHRM has a significant and positive impact on EP and PMN is partially mediating between the two. Positive moderation was found on the GHRM-EP linkage in terms of green values. The results of this study add to the existing research for GHRM in non-Western contexts and have practical value for HR managers and professionals of SMEs looking to institutionalize environmental sustainability.

INTRODUCTION

Environmental degradation is one of the more serious issues of modern societies. Over the years there has been a loss in biodiversity, and habitat destruction and degradation have led to the government and researchers looking for structured interventions (Hooi et al., 2022). Increasingly, scholarly attention has turned to organizational practices as means to reduce the ecological harm caused and there is increased agreement that the effects cannot be reversed through a coordinated and sustained effort (Shafaei et al., 2020). The

scientific community and environmental policy makers have largely concurred that humanity plays a key role in issues like depletion of resources, increasing pollution and biodiversity loss (Mtutu & Thondhlana, 2016; Renwick et al., 2013). This background sets the stage for the inclusion of environmental responsibility in the management of organizations, which is now a necessity instead of an option (Gill et al., 2023).

In organizations, HRM is considered as a pillar to environmental outcomes. Incorporating sustainable activities into daily operations of

employees creates a positive influence on the overall company's scores on environmental metrics (Nisar et al., 2021). The recognition has been attracting academic and practitioner interest in GHRM which is a method where the organization enables the employees to develop an environmentally conscious attitude (Anwar et al., 2020).

GHRM is the linkage of HR activities to environment management goals that aim to increase awareness of employees to use resources responsibly (Muisyo & Qin, 2021). A positive approach to environmental issues can be created through recruitment, training, performance appraisal and reward management, etc. which can help build an organization's workforce that is pro-environmental (Fawehinmi et al., 2020).

Environmental performance at the individual level is an indicator of how the employee's actions in the work place contribute to the organization's environmental goals (Gill et al., 2021). Research has shown that the knowledge of employees about the environmental impact of their actions will increase their likelihood to behave in an eco-friendly way, thereby promoting the company's environmental performance (Chen and Chang, 2013). Research also has shown that greener production processes come with certain advantages in terms of organizational and individual performance, in part due to the fact that greener processes lead to less material waste. (Kodua et al., 2022)

It is believed that employee engagement in environmentally friendly behaviour is considered as the bases of creating an environmentally responsible organization (Saeed et al., 2019). If employees internalize the norms of the environment and have an authentic sense of responsibility, their work practices are likely to be oriented in this direction. The internalized sense of obligation is closely related to the construct Personal Moral Norms (PMN) as defined by Schwartz (1977) as feelings of moral duty that direct actions toward prosocial behavior. Employees who have high scores in PMN believe that their conduct in ethically charged situations is a personal responsibility (Leonard et al., 2004) and judgments are made on conduct based on personal

values (Thogersen, 2007) are influenced by these norms. Studies indicate that employees are motivated to respond to PMN when they become aware of environmental issues, know the consequences if they do not act on the problem, and feel responsible for the consequences (Bamberg et al., 2007). GHRM can play its part in this awareness by bringing attention of the organization towards environmental sustainability (Saeed et al., 2019).

In the previous literature, the relationship between GHRM and environmental performance is shown positive (Muisyo & Qin, 2021; Tang et al., 2018) and previous studies have revealed that green employee behaviour acts as a mediator between GHRM and environmental performance (Guerci et al., 2016). Empirical research on GHRM, however, has been limited in some aspects, especially in non-Western settings (Renwick et al., 2013), among some scholars. According to Ahmad (2015) there is a lack of comprehensive GHRM study in developing countries and across the Asian region in particular which this study strives to fill in.

This study has an empirical background of Lahore, Pakistan which is facing a severe pollution problem. Poor air quality caused by automobiles, industrial pollution and extensive urban development has led to a significant increase in respiratory and other illness associated with pollution. In such a setting, the importance of both adopting environmentally responsible HR practices in local organizations and adhering to these practices becomes heightened. Corporate actions like carpooling, reducing energy consumption in the workspace, creating sustainable supply chains and promoting remote work are just a few practical examples that can help companies lower their ecological footprint and further embed their CSR in the organization.

PMN serving as an intervening mechanism while GV functions as a moderating condition, anchored within Bandura's (1986) Social Cognitive Theory which suggests that GHRM influences employees' attitudes, norms, and values which in turn leads to better environmental performance levels. This study is one of the few studies conducted in Pakistan on GHRM and

seeks to provide practical implications for organizations seeking to integrate sustainability into their HRM.

Literature Review

In this study Social Cognitive Theory (SCT) proposed by Bandura (1986) is used. SCT has a belief that human behavior is a product of a three-part interaction between the individual, behavior, and the environment. Purposive behavior is a result of prior experience, knowledge and personal attitudes; it is influenced by reciprocal interactions between the individual and social and physical context. In the context of the current study, SCT implies that practices of GHRM can be viewed as stimuli in the organization through which employees' environmental knowledge is cultivated and norms and values that support the adoption of an environmentally responsible approach are reinforced.

SCT also acknowledges that moral norms can be developed through social and organizational processes (Hogg, 2016). If employees see their organization being responsive to environmental sustainability, they are more apt to take it as a norm in their own thinking. Organizational norms become personal norms and influence individual actions as they become part of the workplace socialization process (Arnaud & Sekerka, 2010). Employees' perception of an organization that actively pursues environmental sustainability via GHRM will then lead to employees' feeling of a moral responsibility to the environment and a sense of green values influencing their behaviour. These internal states, in turn, are expected to be related to higher levels of environmental performance. In line with this argument, SCT suggests that structural barriers and organizational support are important factors to consider when studying what impedes or facilitates an individual's ability to act in a manner that demonstrates environmental performance, which can be addressed with a well-designed GHRM (Bandura, 1999; Nisar et al., 2021; Singh et al., 2020).

GHRM and EP

GHRM is a set of human resource practices that contribute to the development of environmental

sustainability through dimensions of social equity, employee health and wellbeing and the organizational goals of ecological and economic balance (Amrutha & Geetha, 2020). To measure the effectiveness of an organization's environmental policies in practice, environmental performance serves as an indicator of the organization's environmental impact (Aftab et al., 2023). If GHRM is integrated into HR processes, companies create not just an environmentally conscious workforce, but one that is also driven to take action. This orientation is good for the environment, the reputation of the organization, and employee engagement. Robust empirical evidence has established that there is a positive relationship between GHRM and EP (Mousa & Othman, 2020; Saeed et al., 2019; Benevene & Buonomo, 2020; Gilal et al., 2019). The hypothesis is that, based on this evidence, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H1: GHRM exerts a significant positive effect on EP.

GHRM and PMN

GHRM is an active approach that integrates environmental conscious approaches into the HR processes to minimize the ecological impact of employees and facilitate business growth towards sustainability (Lakhera & Sharma, 2020). Personal moral norms, on the other hand, are internalized beliefs an individual has about what is right and wrong along with the feeling of responsibility that these beliefs create in certain situations (Raymond & Schneider, 2014). The organizational culture and work environment changes as a result of organizational implementation of GHRM, which can change employees' attitudes towards environmental responsibility (Makarim & Muafi, 2021). GHRM has been proven to create a green passion within the employees, leading to a greater environmental identity and a stronger personal sense of values that match the company's environmental goals (Astakhova & Porter, 2015). Based on this, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H2: GHRM significantly and positively predicts PMN.

PMN and EP

Within moral behavior frameworks, personal moral norms occupy a central and influential position and have been found to be good predictors of ethical conduct in various contexts (Veseli et al., 2021). In the environmental aspect, the application of personal moral standards could be a driving mechanism that fosters responsible practices among individuals and influence general sustainability efforts (Fawehinmi et al., 2020). This is because a person's moral norms directly influence their tendency to engage in pro-environmental actions, which has been evidenced in several studies (Kacha & van der Linden, 2021). People with strong environmental values that stem from the sense of stewardship and responsibility are more likely to make conscious decisions, to use less energy, to recycle, choose more sustainable products, and to promote sustainable action in others. This relationship is expressed in the following hypothesis:

H3: PMN positively and significantly predicts EP

PMN functioning as an intervening mechanism linking GHRM to EP

To attain good environmental performance, there is a need to have meaningful link between the GHRM and employee's enacted green behavior. This connection is usually made by internal psychological processes like moral norms that act as a process linking organizational practices to individual behaviour (Fawehinmi et al., 2020). Although empirical studies on PMN acting as a mediator between GHRM and EP are few, similar studies have shown that moral norms act as a mediator between environmental factors, such as environmental self-identity, and outcomes such as

green employee behavior (Pronello & Gaborieau, 2018; Van der Werff et al., 2013). In light of this theoretical and empirical support, a hypothesis is developed:

H4: PMN acts as a mediator between GHRM and EP.

The Role of GV as Moderator

Green values are a person's tendency to consider environmental protection when they are buying and consuming products (Haws et al., 2014). Green values have been identified as a relatively undocumented aspect of corporate green initiatives and are therefore the need for further investigation into their part in environmental management (Hooi et al., 2022; Roscoe et al., 2019). Conceptually, GHRM and green values are interlinked, as GHRM gives an organizational structure for green values to be put into practice in HR practice. Empirical studies revealed a positive relation between GHRM and green values (Alzgoor, 2019; Muisyo et al., 2022), and some researchers also highlighted that the employees' eco-centric values are a prerequisite for the success of environment handling programs (Hooi et al., 2022). Although green values are considered to play a moderating role in the GHRM-EP relationship, little empirical research has focused on this topic so far (Dumont et al., 2017). This research suggests that the impact of GHRM on environmental performance is more powerful if there is a stronger green value among the employees. On these bases the following hypothesis is proposed:

H5: GV moderates the role between the EP and the GHRM

Figure1: Theoretical Model

Methodology

Data Collection & Sample Size

In this study, the research design that is used is exploratory quantitative research design, which is based on primary empirical data as shown in Figure 2. The data was gathered from employees of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) of Lahore, Pakistan, which included both face to face survey administration and online survey administration.

Sample size is an important consideration in SEM. There are a number of conventions in the literature: a minimum of five, and as many as 100 participants per construct variable (Sencan 2005) or ten or more observations per construct variable (a more conservative convention). The number of 200 is generally agreed to be sufficient for meaningful factor analysis (Chen et al., 2020), and a sample size less than 150 tends to be too small for confirmatory factor analysis and SEM (Morewedge et al., 2021). Based on these thresholds, data was gathered from 281

respondents, which is more than the usual 200 (Baykal & Bayraktar, 2022).

Construct Measurement

All the measurement scales were modified from existing validated scales. The GHRM was measured by the five items scale developed by Dumont et al. (2017) and later adopted by Sabokro et al. (2021) where the word company was replaced by word university to reflect the study context. The environmental performance was measured with 14 items taken from Larran Jorge et al (2016) which acknowledged EP on a university campus. PMN were measured using four items drawn from the scales of Ruepert et al. (2017) and Steg and De Groot (2010). GV were captured through a four-item instrument developed from Dumont et al. (2017) and Chou (2014). Each item was rated on a scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Because of the time and resource limitations purposive sampling was used as a data collection method.

Figure 2: Flowchart of Research Methodology

4. Analysis and Results:

Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) is used as a second-generation approach which allows testing of multiple independent and dependent variables in concert, based on an hypothesized interrelationship. Within a structured model, correlations can be measured directly by means of SEM; the variables that are directly measurable are known as manifest variables, the variables that influence the correlation between these manifest variables are referred to as latent variables. Partial Least Squares (PLS), a component centered technique for structural equation modeling, was developed by Wold in 1975 as variance-based and is known as flexible in dealing with data that are not normally distributed. SmartPLS has been used for analyzing structural models.

4.1 Reliability and Model Fit:

On the basis of methodological approach used in this research, PLS-SEM was chosen for the analysis of hypotheses. Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was used to determine the constructs' reliability and validity. Through the use of Cronbach's alpha coefficient, internal consistency or reliability of the constructs were evaluated. Cronbach's alpha has several standard values, 0.70 is a common threshold, while a higher (> 0.80) is preferred in certain situations. In the present study, the reliability of the study is 0.94. Construct-level reliability values are presented in Table 1, with item-level detail provided in Annex 1. Model adequacy was assessed through PLS-SEM. SRMR thresholds distinguish small (> 0.2), medium (> 0.1), and large (> 0.0) effect sizes. A moderate SRMR (0.09) is provided for a model of the

structure. Structural equation modeling (SEM) constructs that have composite reliability > 0.40 are selected for analysis (Geldhof et al. 2014; Rafi

et al. 2022). As can be seen in Table 1, the reliabilities of all constructs were above 0.60 and were composite reliabilities.

Table 1. Factor Loading of Each Item Construct

Measurement Items		Factor Loading	Cronbach's alpha
Green Human Resource Management	GHRM1	0.67	0.86
	GHRM2	0.86	
	GHRM3	0.79	
	GHRM4	0.91	
	GHRM5	0.72	
Environmental Performance	EP1	0.72	0.92
	EP2	0.67	
	EP3	0.52	
	EP4	0.47	
	EP5	0.87	
	EP6	0.65	
	EP7	0.83	
	EP8	0.70	
	EP9	0.66	
	EP10	0.43	
	EP11	0.79	
	EP12	0.84	
	EP13	0.84	
	EP14	0.71	
Personal Moral Norms	PMN1	0.87	0.81
	PMN2	0.90	
	PMN3	0.89	
	PMN4	0.46	
Green Value	GV1	0.86	0.87
	GV2	0.80	
	GV3	0.85	
	GV4	0.87	

4.2 Correlation Matrix

The current results showed that GHRM had a significant positive correlation with gender among the control variables ($r = 0.32, p < 0.01$). Work experience was also found to be positively related to GHRM ($r = 0.11, p < 0.01$) and there was also a positive association between GHRM and education level ($r = 0.03, p < 0.01$). However, sector

type showed a negative relationship with GHRM ($r = -0.13, p < 0.01$) as shown in Table 2.

At the construct level, EP and GHRM demonstrated a significant positive correlation ($r = 0.60, p < 0.01$). PMN was similarly correlated with GHRM in a positive direction ($r = 0.45, p < 0.01$), and GV followed the same pattern ($r = 0.55, p < 0.01$), as presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Correlation Analysis of Variables

	Gender	Age	Education	Experience	Sector	GHRM	EP	PMN	GV
Gender	1								
Age	-.33**	1							
Education	-.18**	.41**	1						
Experience	-.23**	.80**	.39**	1					
Sector	-.29**	.17**	-.16**	.06	1				
GHRM	.32**	-.06	.03	.11	-.13*	1			
EP	.19**	-.27**	.01	-.10	-.18**	.60**	1		
PMN	-.11	.17**	.14*	.32**	.37**	.45**	.38**	1	
GV	.10	-.06	.14*	-.01	.24**	.55**	.70**	.73**	1

Significant at $p < 0.01$ (two-tailed).

Significant at $p < 0.05$ (two-tailed).

4.3 Structural Model

Path coefficients estimation, bootstrapping and significance of the hypotheses were performed using SmartPLS. In this way, it was possible to analyze direct and indirect relationships in details within the proposed framework. The results from each of the five hypothesis tests are summarized in Table 3.

At the secondary and tertiary levels, GHRM has become a key determinant to the environmental consequences. Institutions which include GHRM as an integral part of their operation cultures are more likely to induce changes in the direction of sustainability. The reinforcing nature of the personal moral norms and green values also focuses the possible effect of these practices.

Table 3. Summary of Hypothesis

	Hypothesis	Path Coefficient	Significance	Outcome
H1	GHRM positively and significantly predicts EP.	0.38	$p < 0.01$	Supported
H2	GHRM positively and significantly predicts PMN.	0.22	$p < 0.01$	Supported
H3	PMN positively and significantly predicts EP.	0.13	$p < 0.01$	Supported
H4	PMN plays a mediating role between the EP and the GHRM.	0.03	$p < 0.01$	Supported
H5	GV acts a moderater between EP and the GHRM.	0.09	$p < 0.01$	Supported

H1 was: There is a strong relationship between GHRM and environmental performance. This prediction is confirmed by the results in Table 3, which shows the statistically significant ($p < 0.01$) path coefficient of 0.38, which means that the

practice of GHRM is meaningfully positive and related to environmental performance in SMEs. Hypothesis H2 put forward that the positive effect of GHRM on personal moral norms. A path coefficient of 0.22 ($p < 0.01$) proves this: the greater the GHRM practices are, the greater the moral

norms of employees tend to be in the direction of taking care of the environment.

In the direct link between personal moral norms and environmental performance, the hypothesis H3 was investigated. path coefficient value of 0.13 ($p < 0.01$) validated that there is a significant positive relationship and that employees with higher moral standards have better environmental performance.

Findings from the hypothesis H4 suggest that personal moral norms mediate the GHRM-EP

relationship. This mediation is supported by its indirect path coefficient of 0.03 ($p < 0.01$), which means that GHRM plays a mediating role that is psychologically mediated.

The GHRM-EP relationship was tested in Hypothesis H5 to determine if green values moderate that relationship. It is supported by the path coefficient, which is 0.09 ($p < 0.01$) as the effect of green values of employees on environmental performance is stronger when the employees' green values are stronger.

Fig 3: Structural Equation Model with path coefficient

Path coefficients explain how strong the relationships are between latent constructs and their direction. The 2.5% and 97.5% confidence intervals were employed to establish a statistically reliable range for estimating the actual population

parameters. Notably, the value of path coefficient is 0.72, which indicates a strong and proven positive relationship between GHRM and environmental performance. This statement can be supported by the confidence interval (0.66,

0.78). Likewise, the path coefficient of green values to environmental performance is conspicuous at 0.79 and the confidence interval of this path is 0.72 to 0.86, which further strengthens this observation with a higher level of confidence. The result of path coefficient is 0.64, which shows that there is a moderate to strong positive correlation with confidence interval between 0.51 and 0.75 between green values and green human resource management. Moreover, a path coefficient of 0.39 means that the relationship between the path from personal moral norms to

environmental performance is significant and positive with 95% CI being (0.29, 0.53). A positive correlation between GHRM and personal moral standards is suggested by the path coefficient, which is 0.21 with a 95% confidence interval of (0.13, 0.35). Finally, a path coefficient of 0.37 indicates a positive association between green values and personal moral standards, which is supported by the confidence interval between 0.25 and 0.50, strengthening the strength of this relationship.

Table 4. Monotrait and Hetrotrait

	Sample Estimate	Lower CI (2.5%)	Upper CI (97.5%)
GHRM - EP	0.72	0.66	0.78
GV - EP	0.79	0.79	0.86
GV - GHRM	0.64	0.51	0.75
PMN - EP	0.39	0.29	0.53
PMN - GHRM	0.21	0.13	0.35
PMN - GV	0.37	0.25	0.50

Discussion

The objective of this research was to investigate the impact of GHRM practices on environmental performance in the context of Pakistani small and medium enterprises (SMEs), where the personal moral norms act as a mediator and green values as a moderator. The results show that GHRM perceptions in the organizations studied were slightly lower than anticipated, however, the results have confirmed the theorized relationships. A structural problem emerges from the gap between commitment and action: The commitment to the environment is not necessarily reflected in the actual environmental performance, even if employees are motivated to act in an environmentally responsible way, they may find it hard to do so, given the environment in which they work. This is especially relevant for SMEs in Pakistan because, as size increases, and in more developed economic settings, institutional support for environmental management generally becomes stronger. To close this gap, we need policy statements which include environmental sustainability to be integrated into the daily routines and the evaluation systems of the organization.

Environmental performance is a concept that encompasses measurable results that individuals and organizations have on the natural environment. It is located at the cross-section of the economy, social engagement and the environment, seeking it is in line with the broader goals of sustainable development. GHRM is involved with EP by integrating environmental aspects in HR processes, thus shape a sustainability-oriented workforce. The current findings demonstrate a positive influence of GHRM on EP, aligning with evidence reported in earlier scholarship (Ashraful et al., 2021; Mousa & Othman, 2020).

This positive impact of GHRM on personal moral norms is also verified. Employees are more likely to acquire or strengthen moral norms aligned with their view of their company's real commitment to environmentally responsible behaviors (Afsar & Umrani, 2020; Fawehinmi et al., 2020). This result indicates that employees' normative orientations to the environment do not exist in a vacuum but react to organizational practices and cues.

This positive association between personal moral norms and environmental performance is

noteworthy as it points to some significant aspects of the process by which personal values turn into behaviors. Incorporating moral standards is a form of green HR practice which, in turn, helps employees embrace the job more and get motivated. The current results are consistent with emerging evidence that high PMN is linked to pro-environmental actions and sustainability outcomes (Krettenauer & Lefebvre, 2021; Veseli et al., 2021).

The findings from the mediation suggest that PMN is a route of influence through which GHRM exert influence on EP. The results are consistent with theory and research demonstrating that the effect of behavioral activators occurs at least in part through the formation of internalized moral norms (Pronello & Gaborieau, 2018), although no previous study seems to have directly tested this mediation. The pathway GHRM to PMN to EP could be considered as evidence of the psychological mechanism by which green HR practices influence environmental behaviour in practice, as Green HR practices are tied to moral norms.

With respect to moderation, the study has validated the enhancement of this positive effect with green values on EP using GHRM. The benefits of GHRM in terms of enhanced environmental performance are greater if the surrounding environment of the organizations has a high level of green values among the employees. GHRM effectiveness is still less where there are no or less-developed green values. This underlines the need not only of implementing GHRM practices but also adopting value systems among employees which enable these practices to take complete effect.

Practical Implications

The results of this study have practical applications for organizations that want to incorporate sustainability into their HRM strategies. There are additional benefits of embedding GHRM practices; it also influences employees' beliefs, norms and values, which have an impact on sustainability-related commitment within the organization that is more durable and internal.

The findings highlight the need to establish green HRM policies based on well-defined

organizational values, especially in the context of SME management. Organizations should convey environmental ideals in recruitment to ensure that candidates with an interest in that ideal are drawn to the organization. After achieving the buy-in, the green habits of the employees should be perpetuated by uniform policy-implementation and by organizational culture.

There are also opportunities for HR departments to directly contribute to creating environmental awareness by using training programs, seminars and awareness campaigns. Staff should be made aware of the impact of their daily actions in the workplace such as batteries, paper, plastic and glass and given practical ways to limit the impacts.

Connecting environmental performance with formal processes and monetary or otherwise incentives for responsible conduct is another way that organizations can promote environmentally responsible behaviours. Opportunities for employees should be structured to enable them to provide feedback and observations to the policy-making process, which may help them feel more responsible for the environmental outcomes. Organizations can communicate their values related to the environment in job descriptions and can structure questions for interviews to assess consistency with organizational values.

Limitations And Future Recommendations

This study has some limitations. Firstly, the data was gathered only from the SMEs of Lahore and therefore the findings cannot be generalized. Some other cities like Karachi and Islamabad in Pakistan have unique organizational culture and economy, and repetition of the study in these cities would be useful in attesting the transferability of the relationships found in this study. Expansion of the research to other countries, in particular other developing and emerging economies would also help to gain a more complete comparative understanding of the role that cultural context plays in the GHRM-EP relationship.

Second, PMN was identified as a mediator of the GHRM-EP relationship but the indirect path coefficient was relatively small (0.03). Other mediators are worth investigating in future research to potentially reinforce this pathway.

Transformational environmental leadership, senior management commitment, and workplace spirituality may be valuable variables that were previously shown to relate to pro-environmental motivation (Graves & Sarkis, 2018; Afsar et al., 2016) and could be fruitful additions to the models.

Third, this study used self-administered quantitative questionnaire as a tool to collect data and although it has its merits in hypothesis testing, it fails to provide the depth and texture of the employees' lived experience. Future studies might employ structured or semi structured qualitative interviews to complement this research and to explore the impact of GHRM on employee attitude and behavior in short and long-term time horizons.

Conclusion

The results of this study demonstrated how green HRM and EGB interact with PMN, which can assist the regime recognize that SMEs are just as crucial to environmental sustainability as other social groups. The ruling body should thus continue to encourage businesses, particularly SMEs, to continue their efforts to ensure that the behavior of their employees is in line with environmental sustainability.

The current study aimed to understand the effect of green HRM on EP of Pakistani personnel through the link of their PMN and GV. The results reveals that green HRM did affect EP, albeit through the full mediation of the two mediators (PMN and GV). Effective green HRM strategies can influence employees' personal standards, which in turn affects their EP.

Research on green HRM is still in its early stages, according to Dumont et al. (2016). The present research aims to raise awareness across various industry sectors regarding the crucial contribution green HRM makes in nurturing eco-conscious conduct among employees, along with the mutual gains this yields for both organizations and the natural environment. HR practitioners are well-positioned to adopt measures that foster a secure working atmosphere alongside a motivated and productive workforce.

Going green is extremely important for not only large companies but also SMEs in the world specifically Pakistan as one of the developing countries. Businesses are under immense pressure to deliver to the needs of numerous parts of the globe, but, in the process, environmental degradation has been causing damage to the ecosystem.

References

- Afsar, B., Badir, Y., & Kiani, U. S. (2016). Linking spiritual leadership and employee pro-environmental behavior: The influence of workplace spirituality, intrinsic motivation, and environmental passion. *Journal of Environmental Psychology, 45*, 79-88.
- Afsar, B., & Umrani, W. A. (2020). Corporate social responsibility and pro-environmental behavior at workplace: The role of moral reflectiveness, coworker advocacy, and environmental commitment. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management, 27*(1), 109-125.
- Aftab, J., Abid, N., Cucari, N., & Savastano, M. (2023). Green human resource management and environmental performance: The role of green innovation and environmental strategy in a developing country. *Business Strategy and the Environment, 32*(4), 1782-1798.
- Ahmad, S. (2015). Green human resource management: Policies and practices. *Cogent business & management, 2*(1), 1030817.
- Alzgoool, M. (2019). Nexus between green HRM and green management towards fostering green values. *Management Science Letters, 9*(12), 2073-2082.
- Amrutha, V., & Geetha, S. (2020). A systematic review on green human resource management: Implications for social sustainability. *Journal of Cleaner production, 247*, 119131.

- Anwar, N., Mahmood, N. H. N., Yusliza, M. Y., Ramayah, T., Faezah, J. N., & Khalid, W. (2020). Green Human Resource Management for organizational citizenship behaviour towards the environment and environmental performance on a university campus. *Journal of Cleaner production*, 256, 120401.
- Arnaud, A., & Sekerka, L. E. (2010). Positively ethical: The establishment of innovation in support of sustainability. *International Journal of Sustainable Strategic Management*, 2(2), 121-137.
- Ashraful, A. M., Niu, X., & Rounok, N. (2021). Effect of green human resource management (GHRM) overall on organization's environmental performance: The mediating role of green employee empowerment. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science (2147-4478)*, 10(4), 99-116.
- Astakhova, M. N., & Porter, G. (2015). Understanding the work passion-performance relationship: The mediating role of organizational identification and moderating role of fit at work. *Human relations*, 68(8), 1315-1346.
- Bamberg, S., Hunecke, M., & Blöbaum, A. (2007). Social context, personal norms and the use of public transportation: Two field studies. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 27(3), 190-203.
- Bandura, A. (1986). Social foundations of thought and action. *Englewood Cliffs, NJ*, 1986(23-28).
- Bandura, A. (1999). Social cognitive theory of personality. *Handbook of personality*, 2, 154-196.
- Baykal, E., & Bayraktar, O. (2022). Green human resources management: A novel tool to boost work engagement. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 951963.
- Benevene, P., & Buonomo, I. (2020). Green human resource management: An evidence-based systematic literature review. *Sustainability*, 12(15), 5974.
- Chen, H., Richard, O. C., Boncoeur, O. D., & Ford Jr, D. L. (2020). Work engagement, emotional exhaustion, and counterproductive work behavior. *Journal of Business Research*, 114, 30-41.
- Chou, C.-J. (2014). Hotels' environmental policies and employee personal environmental beliefs: Interactions and outcomes. *Tourism management*, 40, 436-446.
- Dumont, J., Shen, J., & Deng, X. (2017). Effects of green HRM practices on employee workplace green behavior: The role of psychological green climate and employee green values. *Human resource management*, 56(4), 613-627.
- Fawehinmi, O., Yusliza, M., Wan Kasim, W. Z., Mohamad, Z., & Sofian Abdul Halim, M. A. (2020). Exploring the interplay of green human resource management, employee green behavior, and personal moral norms. *Sage Open*, 10(4), 2158244020982292.
- Geldhof, G. J., Preacher, K. J., & Zyphur, M. J. (2014). Reliability estimation in a multilevel confirmatory factor analysis framework. *Psychological methods*, 19(1), 72.
- Gilal, F. G., Ashraf, Z., Gilal, N. G., Gilal, R. G., & Channa, N. A. (2019). Promoting environmental performance through green human resource management practices in higher education institutions: A moderated mediation model. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 26(6), 1579-1590.
- Gill, A. A., Farrokh, S., Haider, M. U., & Zubair, R. (2023). Do Green Human Resource Practices Influence Employee Environmental Performance? The Mediating Effect of Proactive Environmental Management Maturity. *Pakistan Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 11(1), 701-709-701-709.

- Gill, A. A., Kazmi, K. R., & Ali, B. (2021). DO GOOD, HAVE GOOD: ANALYZING THE EFFECT OF GREEN HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT PRACTICES ON ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOR TOWARDS THE ENVIRONMENT IN DEVELOPING ECONOMY. *Pakistan Journal of Social Research*, 3(02), 183-192.
- Graves, L. M., & Sarkis, J. (2018). The role of employees' leadership perceptions, values, and motivation in employees' proenvironmental behaviors. *Journal of Cleaner production*, 196, 576-587.
- Guerci, M., Longoni, A., & Luzzini, D. (2016). Translating stakeholder pressures into environmental performance—the mediating role of green HRM practices. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 27(2), 262-289.
- Haws, K. L., Winterich, K. P., & Naylor, R. W. (2014). Seeing the world through GREEN-tinted glasses: Green consumption values and responses to environmentally friendly products. *Journal of consumer psychology*, 24(3), 336-354.
- Hogg, M. A. (2016). *Social identity theory*. Springer.
- Hooi, L. W., Liu, M.-S., & Lin, J. J. (2022). Green human resource management and green organizational citizenship behavior: do green culture and green values matter? *International Journal of Manpower*, 43(3), 763-785.
- Kácha, O., & van der Linden, S. (2021). The moderating role of moral norms and personal cost in compliance with pro-environmental social norms. *Current Research in Ecological and Social Psychology*, 2, 100020.
- Kodua, L. T., Xiao, Y., Adjei, N. O., Asante, D., Ofosu, B. O., & Amankona, D. (2022). Barriers to green human resources management (GHRM) implementation in developing countries. Evidence from Ghana. *Journal of Cleaner production*, 340, 130671.
- Krettenauer, T., & Lefebvre, J. P. (2021). Beyond subjective and personal: Endorsing pro-environmental norms as moral norms. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 76, 101644.
- Lakhera, A., & Sharma, P. (2020). Green HRM: Best HR Practices Within an Organization for Reducing Employees' Carbon Footprint. *International Journal of Knowledge-Based Organizations (IJKBO)*, 10(3), 1-8.
- Larrán Jorge, M., Herrera Madueño, J., Calzado, Y., & Andrades, J. (2016). A proposal for measuring sustainability in universities: a case study of Spain. *International Journal of Sustainability in Higher Education*, 17(5), 671-697.
- Makarim, A. F., & Muafi, M. (2021). The effect of green human resource management (GHRM) practices on turnover intention: Mediating role of work environment. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science (2147-4478)*, 10(5), 83-94.
- Morewedge, C. K., Monga, A., Palmatier, R. W., Shu, S. B., & Small, D. A. (2021). Evolution of consumption: A psychological ownership framework. *Journal of Marketing*, 85(1), 196-218.
- Mousa, S. K., & Othman, M. (2020). The impact of green human resource management practices on sustainable performance in healthcare organizations: A conceptual framework. *Journal of Cleaner production*, 243, 118595.
- Mtutu, P., & Thondhlana, G. (2016). Encouraging pro-environmental behaviour: Energy use and recycling at Rhodes University, South Africa. *Habitat International*, 53, 142-150.
- Muisyo, P. K., & Qin, S. (2021). Enhancing the FIRM'S green performance through green HRM: The moderating role of green innovation culture. *Journal of Cleaner production*, 289, 125720.

- Muisyo, P. K., Su, Q., Hashmi, H. B. A., Ho, T. H., & Julius, M. M. (2022). The role of green HRM in driving hotels' green creativity. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 34(4), 1331-1352.
- Nisar, Q. A., Haider, S., Ali, F., Jamshed, S., Ryu, K., & Gill, S. S. (2021). Green human resource management practices and environmental performance in Malaysian green hotels: The role of green intellectual capital and pro-environmental behavior. *Journal of Cleaner production*, 311, 127504.
- Pronello, C., & Gaborieau, J.-B. (2018). Engaging in pro-environment travel behaviour research from a psycho-social perspective: A review of behavioural variables and theories. *Sustainability*, 10(7), 2412.
- Rafi, N., Ahmed, A., Shafique, I., & Kalyar, M. N. (2022). Knowledge management capabilities and organizational agility as liaisons of business performance. *South Asian Journal of Business Studies*, 11(4), 397-417.
- Raymond, L., & Schneider, L. U. (2014). Personal moral norms and attitudes toward endangered species policies on private land. *Conservation and Society*, 12(1), 1-15.
- Renwick, D. W., Redman, T., & Maguire, S. (2013). Green human resource management: A review and research agenda. *International journal of management reviews*, 15(1), 1-14.
- Roscoe, S., Subramanian, N., Jabbour, C. J., & Chong, T. (2019). Green human resource management and the enablers of green organizational culture: Enhancing a firm's environmental performance for sustainable development. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 28(5), 737-749.
- Ruepert, A. M., Keizer, K., & Steg, L. (2017). The relationship between Corporate Environmental Responsibility, employees' biospheric values and pro-environmental behaviour at work. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 54, 65-78.
- Sabokro, M., Masud, M. M., & Kayedian, A. (2021). The effect of green human resources management on corporate social responsibility, green psychological climate and employees' green behavior. *Journal of Cleaner production*, 313, 127963.
- Saeed, B. B., Afsar, B., Hafeez, S., Khan, I., Tahir, M., & Afridi, M. A. (2019). Promoting employee's proenvironmental behavior through green human resource management practices. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 26(2), 424-438.
- Şencan, H. (2005). *Güvenilirlik ve geçerlilik*. Hüner Şencan.
- Shafaei, A., Nejati, M., & Yusoff, Y. M. (2020). Green human resource management: A two-study investigation of antecedents and outcomes. *International Journal of Manpower*, 41(7), 1041-1060.
- Singh, S. K., Del Giudice, M., Chierici, R., & Graziano, D. (2020). Green innovation and environmental performance: The role of green transformational leadership and green human resource management. *Technological forecasting and social change*, 150, 119762.
- Steg, L., & De Groot, J. (2010). Explaining prosocial intentions: Testing causal relationships in the norm activation model. *British journal of social psychology*, 49(4), 725-743.
- Tang, G., Chen, Y., Jiang, Y., Paillé, P., & Jia, J. (2018). Green human resource management practices: scale development and validity. *Asia pacific journal of human resources*, 56(1), 31-55.
- Van der Werff, E., Steg, L., & Keizer, K. (2013). It is a moral issue: The relationship between environmental self-identity, obligation-based intrinsic motivation and pro-environmental behaviour. *Global environmental change*, 23(5), 1258-1265.

Veseli, B., Koch, E., Soliman, M., Sandner, S., Studte, S., & Clement, M. (2021). The role of affect, satisfaction and internal drive on personal moral norms during COVID-19. *ISBT Science Series*, 16(2), 158-167.

